

NON-UNIVERSAL HUMAN RIGHTS: WESTERN AND LATIN AMERICAN CONTRIBUTIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF A MORE COMPLETE HUMAN BEING¹

DIREITOS HUMANOS NÃO UNIVERSAIS: AS CONTRIBUIÇÕES OCIDENTAIS E AS CONTRIBUIÇÕES LATINO-AMERICANAS PARA A FORMAÇÃO DE UM SER HUMANO MAIS COMPLETO

Vitória dos Santos Acerbi²
Felipe Costa Lima (coordinator)³

ABSTRACT: The goal of this article is to map and analyse Western and Latin American contributions to human rights. Firstly, we will highlight the value and limits of the former, which have been hegemonically universalized; secondly, we will explicit the latter, 'silenced' systems of thought which have been violently suppressed by colonial and postcolonial forces thus far. By bringing to light these 'new' human rights' understandings and perspectives, this text aims to build a fruitful and horizontal epistemological dialogue in this area, thus ultimately contributing to a less incomplete universality of human rights and to a more complete human being.

KEYWORDS: Western human rights history; Latin American human rights history; ecology of knowledge; universal human rights; postcolonial studies.

RESUMO: O objetivo deste artigo é mapear e analisar as contribuições ocidentais e latino-americanas para os direitos humanos. Primeiro, destacaremos o valor e os limites das primeiras, universalizadas hegemonicamente; em seguida, explicitaremos as segundas, sistemas de pensamento 'silenciados' que foram violentamente reprimidos pelas forças coloniais e pós-coloniais. Trazendo à luz esses 'novos' entendimentos e perspectivas dos direitos humanos, este texto pretende construir um diálogo epistemológico frutífero e horizontal nesta área e, em última instância, contribuir para uma universalidade menos incompleta dos direitos humanos e para um ser humano mais completo.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: História ocidental dos direitos humanos; história latino-americana dos direitos humanos; ecologia do conhecimento; direitos humanos universais; estudos pós-coloniais.

¹ This article integrates the Line 3 of the Projeto Integrador Estudos Pesquisas (Studying and Researching Integrated Project, in English) called 'Human Rights are not yet universal: The contributions from other epistemologies to a more 'human' human rights', supervised by Prof. Felipe Costa Lima, at Direito Internacional sem Fronteiras (International Law without Borders, in English), available at www.direitointernacionalsemfronteiras.com

² Master's student in Latin American Studies at the University of Salamanca (Usal), Spain, fully funded by Usal/Santander. Currently an Erasmus+ Research Fellow at Sciences Po Paris. Member of the DIsF team. Email address: vitoriaacerbi@gmail.com

³ Temporary professor at the University of Strasbourg (UNISTRA), France; PhD candidate in International Law at UNISTRA, and in International Relations at PUC Minas, Brazil (CAPES scholarship) (thesis co-tutelage); Academic mentor at DIsF. Email address: felipecostalimas@gmail.com

eISSN: 2675-3200

Cadernos de Pesquisa Direito Internacional sem Fronteiras, Vol. 2, N.2, 2020.

DOI:

1 INTRODUCTION

It is not uncommon to read about '*universal*' *human rights* in normative texts, declarations of international organizations and academic discussions. The fact that such an expression is used without much discomfort should call for questioning. On the one hand, concerning its *impacts*, there is a 'different geography of rights' worldwide (BARRAGÁN ROMANO, 2017), with different regions of the globe having distinct material realities of regulation, protection, and a guarantee of the rights that, in theory, every human being is equally entitled to and should be fully able to enjoy. On the other hand, regarding its *epistemological origins*, the commonly acknowledged '*universality*' of human rights seems to refer to, in fact, only *one* of its roots: a local - in this case, namely Western - a perspective that turned hegemonically global (SANTOS, 1998). This seems to have left many other perspectives silenced, and their contributions wasted or unknown. In this light, this universality is actually a myth.

In this sense, this article seeks to contribute to the breaking of the narrative of univocal and unitary human rights, then rebuffing its homogeneous practices and conceptions. To achieve this goal, we will demark the contributions from different epistemologies, thus attempting to build a virtuous and dialectical path by the application of an 'ecology of knowledge'⁴ (SANTOS, 2014).

To do so, we shall start examining the well-known and hegemonic Western human rights. Then, we will proceed to the study of the Latin American contributions to human rights, including those generated within the colonial centre of these societies - thus very much linked to its western origins - and also the contributions from its margins.

⁴ Ecology of knowledge means the establishment of a horizontal dialogue between Modernity and oppressed and 'silenced' worldviews, recognizing the plurality of knowledge existing in the world, outside the hegemonic Western matrix that presents itself as universal and complete.

We must recognise that our objective is enormous. Nevertheless, this is just the first part of our work, considering that this theoretical philosophical discussion seems to us a prerequisite to achieve the foremost goal of this research project, which is to contribute in practice to a more embracing and human 'human rights'. In this line of thinking, beyond that 20% per cent of the globe's population that has been universalising its regional worldview since the colonial epoch, there is another 80% per cent struggling to be heard. We shall here seek to hear Latin American, creole but also and mainly 'subaltern' worldviews since it will play a fundamental role in building a Transmodern path⁵ (DUSSEL, 2005) to 'universal human rights'.

2 THE WESTERN CONTRIBUTIONS

2.1 THE LIBERAL PERSPECTIVE OF RIGHTS

Disputably said to be produced primarily in/from Europe (with its secularization and laicism, the rational-scientific paradigm of knowledge, as well as with its material developments and social pattern of organization), Modernity gave rise to many changes in the manner in which the individual understood himself, within society and concerning it and the State (QUÍJANO, 1993).

From the Renaissance onwards, the techno-scientific changes made the human body no longer a mystery: although still Godly designed and managed, it was transformed into a decipherable and 'studyable' complex organism. As this new conception took hold in society, it was less socially acceptable to condemn a person's body to torture and to inflict extreme pain

⁵ Transmodernity is global project of liberation in which the Others that were originally excluded from, or victims of, Modernity will equally accomplish themselves in it and live Modernity's emancipation project. That means recognizing the actual incompleteness and partiality of the Western modern project that presents itself as totalizing and consequently it means looking at modern phenomena from the Otherness, from other perspectives, thus promoting an intercultural dialogue.

for redeeming his/her soul, considering that these dimensions of existence were no longer directly associated. (HUNT, 2007)

Additionally, the arts began reshaping conviviality and sensibility. People gradually ceased to be part of a social body - nobility, peasantry, artisans, military, clergy - to be individuals. Epistolary and romantic novels of the 19th century turned their attention to “normal people”, such as maids and ladies or students in love, instead of telling the stories of great kings, warriors, lords and conquerors, as did medieval literature. Paintings equally shifted their focus to genre scenes, portraits of children, women and men who could pay for it, instead of historical scenes and portraits exclusively for nobles. Bourgeois theatres began to have separate chairs for each person instead of a floor for all the crowd to watch the plays together (HUNT, 2007).

These phenomena - the demystification of the human body and the physical and social/cultural singularization of people - led to an appreciation of the person as an individual, a perception that was not socially present before. So, from then on, the person was seen as a unique creature, with feelings and thoughts, encapsulated by a body that had integrity in itself. This conception is in the core of the human being's idea underlying individual liberal rights. (HUNT, 2007)

Still, regarding such rights, we can trace them in time and space, thus precisely demarking their origins and perceiving them as issues of a specific geo-historical experience. The 17th and 18th centuries' ideas as concerns Hobbesian, Lockean and Rousseauian social contracts⁶ came to light and dismantled the theories of the divine rights of kings, which legitimized the social absolutist order. These new understandings coupled with the Enlightenment context have transformed the individual liberties into the essence of any

⁶ It is worth noting that the idea of a social contract as the basis of obligations is by no means a novelty at this point, dating at least of the XI century, if not indeed from Ancient Rome. What made it ground-breaking at this point was its being a result of discussions around rationalist natural law and its perfect articulation with the modern social and political order and paradigm of scientific rationality of them. For more on this matter, see d'Entreves (1972), Lessnoff (1990) and Weinreb (1987).

societal project worthy of such a name, thus heightening its formal regulations and power structure⁷ (SANTOS, 2000).

Roughly, they centred the legitimacy of any government and the sovereignty of the State and its law on the consensual general will of the people, a group of equal individuals endowed with freedom and free will. In this contract, they relinquished a portion of their individual liberties to exist in a regulated whole, embodied in a government in exchange for the protection of these liberties. Then, they could freely pursue their moral and spiritual paths (religion), carry out political and civil tasks (assembly, speech and expression), and also have safeguarded their economic and material goals and outputs (private property) (SANTOS, 2000).

This transformation of people into human beings holders of rights, and the corresponding structuring of a State to assert and guarantee these rights, are intrinsically related to the development of capitalism itself. The *individualization and equalization of persons*, their institutionalized need to think, doubt, decide, legislate, pray for themselves in a free manner go coupled with their embarking in *autonomous and private commercial and industrial enterprises* (QUIJANO, 2005) Likewise, *the metamorphosis of the absolutist State into a Liberal one only makes sense at a time when the regulation and administration of the national State more hinders than favours profit*, in a stage of the capitalist world-system of competitive and free production and commercialization of goods by private-led exploitations, industries and enterprises (WALLERSTEIN, 2011; QUIJANO, 2005).

2.2 THE MARXIAN PERSPECTIVE OF RIGHTS

The development of capitalism had, nevertheless, limits. Within such limits are the modern promises of prosperity and emancipation, that were not materialized for the majority

⁷ As concrete examples of what we are referring to are the U.S. Declaration of Independence of 1776 drafted by Thomas Jefferson, its Bill of Rights Amendment of 1790, as well as the 1789 Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen proclaimed by the French National Assembly. The pretension of Universality of the latter seems to stand out in its very title, as there is no mention of *Frenchman* or *French Citizen*, but rather a more general formulation of *Man and citizen*.

of the population outside the bourgeoisie. This realization progressively took hold in society. Besides, Russia after 1917 gave a tangible example of a political, economic, and social organization that opposed the very basis of capitalism. Thus, *the perception of the deficits in modern capitalist promises and the visible existence of an alternative system gave rise to other perspectives of organizations of the community, market, state.* Ultimately, *they pushed for the emergence of different conceptions and set of rights.* (SANTOS, 2000)

What the Marxian critique comes to argue can be summed up in three main points. Firstly, *the need to transform abstract principles into specific rights that emanate from reality itself.* In other words, human rights statements should attend to the particular historical conditions of a society at a given moment, and thus respond to its concrete needs. (HELLER, 1976). This arises from the Marxian understanding that general principles, such as liberty, are grounded in universal human needs, but they are not autonomous and do not promote automatically when enunciated, a bettering of everybody's lives. On the contrary, they are tied to a social order and hence biasedly instrumentalized in favour of the dominant class and detriment of the dominated ones. (NORDAHL, 1995)

This breaks fundamentally, from the perspective of economic and social classes, the universality proposed by liberal rights. The Marxian critique brings to light the gap between a right proclaimed for all and the conditions in place that actually allow for its enjoyment by a few, thus excluding the majority. In other words, it highlights the fact that the concretion of rights is dependent on economic and social conditions, on the level of development and resource availability in a society (NORDAHL, 1995; ISHAY, 2008).

Secondly, as a Marxian contribution which is derived from the aforementioned, we ought to mention *the conceptualization of the human being as a part of society, and the consequent inscription of his/her rights* and the sole possibility of their realization *in the framework of its social institutions and practices.* In other words, the Marxian approach to human rights comes to say that *as long as we live in a society* (and within it exercise our individual autonomy and

struggle to satisfy our needs) *the extent and quality of the satisfaction of such needs* does not depend solely on our capacity, but *will be forcefully and inevitably determined by the conditions of such society* and its organization, and the possibilities it consequently gives us. (NORDAHL, 1995).

Such a conception culminates in an activation of the provider State, that puts into place conditions of the full enjoyment of labour rights, social security, health and education, culture, and leisure, (BONAVIDES, 1996) thus concreting the equality of human beings in the building of a just society. This responds to the premise that all persons are equally deserving of having their needs met, and that in the institutions and practices of a liberal capitalist State, not all of them are equally able to meet them. (NORDAHL, 1995)

Thirdly, the Marxian approach postulates that *some human rights are inexorably collective rights*. As above mentioned, the equal and full enjoyment of rights only takes place within the society where the individual is inserted in the framework of its institutions and practices, being then dependant on the material conditions and resources availability and distribution. Therefore, some rights cannot be held and exercised by individuals, but by a community as a whole or in some fractions. By way of illustration, the right to economic development can only be held by a society or a nation as a whole; or, in industrialized economies, the right to strike, protest or negotiate, by unions and associations. (NORDAHL, 1995)

2.3 THE LIMITS OF THE WESTERN CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

Both the Liberal and the Marxian propositions clash directly with some pillars of global capitalism. The former builds upon the physical and social autonomy and freedom of individuals, which are affirmed to be all equal. The latter is centred around community, solidarity, and wellbeing, thus allowing for humanity to live in effective conditions of equality. However, in the capitalist world-system, equal humanity was never recognized to every (group of) human being (s) across the continents.

At its very beginning, the capitalist world-system established a hierarchy that involved all the world's population and associated social rank, place and role, type of work - ultimately *human value* - with *race* and *geographical origin*. Such a categorization was so efficacious that it lasted much beyond the colonial project it initially served, being a powerful mental category and axis of organization of the world and its relations of domination ever since. (QUIJANO, 2005).

Thus, the persisting coloniality of power⁸ (QUIJANO, 1997, 2005; MIGNOLO, 2000, 2011) seems to be the abyss (SANTOS & CHAUI, 2014) dividing the world. It establishes the cleavage between the one where liberal and Marxian perspectives circulated in thought and bloomed in rights and the other where they are but a horizon, more or less distant according to the exact point in time, space, and social spectrum one observes. The world where these perspectives of human rights consolidated themselves as regulating forces in the State, market and society, and the world where they are but a theoretical base for scattered and uneven concrete actions and structures. (SANTOS, 2000)

Such an incompleteness and heterogeneity of concreteness of human rights, thus, does not mean that the so-called peripheries of the capitalist world system are permanently, absolutely, and irreversibly in human rights' deficit. These features mean, rather, that they find themselves in a subordinate position that has been built over centuries, hierarchically defining, classifying, and dividing the globe around categories such as race.

They mean, still, that this capitalist world-system has constructed a structure where both the peripheral physical dimensions of existence (bodies, cities, natural environments) and its spiritual and intellectual ones (religions, cosmovisions, philosophies and knowledge) are considered second-class, less valuable and unworthy of attention in comparison to those of the

⁸ The colonial matrix of power, according to decolonial theories, is a complex structure that interconnects different levels of control, such as economic, authority, nature, gender, sexuality, and subjectivity (MIGNOLO, 2008). It articulates the peripheral-central places of international division of labour with the ethnical-racial global division (as well as the above-mentioned forms of control), and constitutes a continuity of colonial power and knowledge systems, that did not end with the political colonial administrations. (GROSFUGUEL, 2008)

capitalist centre. They mean, finally, that the non-Western lines of thinking and practices have neither been yet studied with care and nor put into a fruitful horizontal dialogue with the thus-far dominant Western human rights. As a result, we shall address such a gap, examining and unravelling new knowledge in the following sections.

3 THE LATIN AMERICAN CONTRIBUTIONS

3.1 THE LATIN AMERICAN EARLY MODERN CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

Before the above-mentioned Western contributions, there was a fundamental contribution to human rights from Latin America, although not from Latin American individuals, with a plea for justice based on natural rights made by the Dominican Castilian priest Bartolomé de las Casas. (TIERNEY, 1997)

He articulated at the same time in an innovative way and continuity with a certain tradition of thought. Innovating, he spoke not in a generalist or abstract terms but *reasoned about justice and rights regarding the tangible reality*. Also, *he cultivated his understandings with a thorough observation of the traditions of knowledge and practices of the natives*. Lastly, *he spoke against the hierarchical and colonizing thought*, then at an early phase of development, that classified people according to their race, cultural belonging, and geographical origin. Instead, *he spoke of natives' natural subjective rights* (TIERNEY, 1997), just in virtue of their *humanity*, affirming *equality* among all humans (GUTIÉRREZ, 1993), thus not circumscribing it to Christianity or Europe, but truly universalizing the notion (BEUCHOT, 1994b).

Continuing a catholic theorisation - namely the Aristotelian-Thomist one, also mobilized by other Dominican priests at the school of Salamanca (ANDRÉ-VINCENT, 1974) - he centred his case in defence of Indigenous peoples in their inherent *humanity*, common to all God's children, who were created with *freedom* (DE LAS CASAS, 1995). This concept of freedom was rooted and materialized i) in their understanding and will, ii) in their constitution of the *community*, iii) in their repertoire of creeds and practices, iv) in their *dignity*. Hence, according

to his reasoning, no justification could be found for violence or coercion against their physical or cultural integrity, which should instead be perfected/catechized via persuasion, only. (BEUCHOT, 1994a and b).

Therefore, his novelty is the *application of ideas* that had been circulating in scholar tradition i) to a concrete situation, beyond monasteries and universities; ii) to non-Europeans and non-Christians, until then not thought to be bearers of the same humanity; iii) observing closely the *others* encountered, their cultural and social traits. (CAROZZA, 2003)

It would not be difficult to identify in Las Casas' reasoning elements of what we name the right of a people to self-determination and the right to cultural integrity, evidencing the patent contribution of Latin American to human rights language, both theoretical and practical. Such a parallel can be justified by the not insignificant continuity between the founding Modern thinkers of human rights and contemporary international human rights law (KENNEDY, 1986), and the historical relevance of the formers to several moments and legal texts of the latter (CAROZZA, 2003).

3.2 LATIN AMERICA'S INDEPENDENCES AND THEIR CONTRIBUTIONS TO HUMAN RIGHTS

At the beginning of the 19th century, the constitutions of the new Latin American independent nations⁹ also produced important inputs regarding human rights. Far from mechanically applying the above discussed liberal perspective of rights, widely circulating at the time, these texts have produced robust precedents of constitutionalized individual rights before and sometimes more orthodoxly than the European charters, come later in the century, (MERRYMAN, CLARK & HALEY, 1994). Additionally, the Latin American charters have inscribed the rights in a unique framework of legal and social thought, constituting an important

⁹ To cite only some of the pioneers, we have the constitutions of Haiti (1805), Venezuela (1811), Paraguay (1813), Argentina (1819) Colombia (1821), Peru (1823), El Salvador (1824), Brazil (1824), Guatemala (1825), Nicaragua (1826), Bolivia (1826), Ecuador (1830), Uruguay (1830), Panama (1840) Dominican Republic (1844), Cuba (1869). For more on the matter, see Espiell (2002).

stepstone in the *consolidation of fundamental human rights as a basis for the social contract establishing the national State*. (CAROZZA, 2003),

Such a framework followed the aforesaid pattern of combining traditions of thought with new contributions, arisen of philosophy and/or of concretely experienced processes (CAROZZA, 2003; DE LA TORRE RANGEL, 1994), and with them forging unique systems in harmony with the local mindset. In this case, this mindset was a long-standing yearning for independence, justice, and freedom (ZAVALA, 1964).

As a result, as far as human rights are concerned, these constitutions merged i) principles and practices coming from the *scholastic tradition, jus gentium* and other *Jesuit traditions*, which emphasized doctrines such as the precedence of natural over written law, the legitimate right to refuse despotism and unfair laws, and the imprescriptible character of some rights to which all are entitled to (YEPES, 1962); ii) the *European continental liberal thought* - coming from Rousseau, other thinkers of the Enlightenment, as well as the French Declaration - which emphasized the constructive character of the law as a tool for the instruction and bettering of human beings in society, thus giving a positive outlook on the government constituted thereto; and which influenced the Latin American constitutional texts so as to have a much greater emphasis on equality and fraternity and a lesser one on political liberty or property, if contrasted with the American charter (CAROZZA, 2003,) iii) and finally, the *North American influence*, coming in form of the concepts of public law and judicially enforceable human rights. (CÁRDENAS, 1979)

3.3 THE MEXICAN 1917 CONTRIBUTION

Finally, we could mention another pioneering constitution as an invaluable contribution to universal human rights from Latin America. Born of a national process but in close dialogue with the international context, the Mexican constitution of Querétaro of 1917 is still in force today.

Written at a time when the world was changing fast, shaken by World War I, the Russian Revolution and the deepening of economic globalization, the Mexican charter of 1917 reflected this scenario. It pioneered in recognizing, in such a widely and profoundly changing context, the impossibility of an unchanged permanence of the structures of the State, the dynamics of power, social relations and human rights. Additionally, this text was the very first one in history that can be characterized as a 'social constitution', with its contents focusing on social and economic guarantees and protections as conditions for human dignity and the exercise of human liberty. (CAROZZA, 2003)

Having said that, we cannot seemingly perceive a socialist spirit in the text. Firstly, since it stresses that the human person has rights that precede the State (NORIEGA, 1967). Secondly, because the constitutional congress had delegates from various social and intellectual backgrounds, its debates thus devoid of any precise and structured set of theories or ideologies (NIEMEYER, 1974).

The sources of the 1917 constitution are indicated to be again a plural, theoretical and tangible contributions, combined into something new. (NORIEGA, 1967) To begin with, *a sense of solidarity arisen from the experience of the 1910 revolution and the observation of the concrete reality of the poorest*. Then, *an amalgam of circulating fragments of other countries' progressive legal frameworks*. Last but not least, a persistent presence of *Catholic social doctrines and activism*. This continues with the Latin American tradition of *non-refusal of institutionalized religious contributions to the thinking of human rights*, and last but not least *a search for a balance between the individual and collective facets of human rights*. (NIEMEYER, 1974).

A consequence and proof of the Mexican 1917 constitution's non-socialist character and its connections with the Latin American common ground of human rights concepts is the widespread influence it had on the region's subsequent constitutions. To name but a few, those of Chile (1925), Perú (1925), Uruguay (1934) and Brazil (1934) have been influenced by the Mexican charter. Not to speak of the possible influence in or in any case chronological

precedence to the European wave of social constitutions: the German Weimar charter (1919), the Russian (1919), the Estonian (1920) the Austrian (1920), as well as those of Poland (1921) and Yugoslavia (1921), (PINHEIRO, 2006; COLOMER VIADEL, 1990; RAMOS, 1967)

3.4 THE IMPORTANCE AND THE LIMITS OF THE CONTRIBUTIONS FROM THE LATIN AMERICAN 'INSIDE'

Invaluable as they have been, the Latin American above discussed inputs came from the centres of the societies established in the region within Modernity. These ideas have circulated and have been recognized in doctrine and jurisprudence, although still on a lesser scale than the ones issued directly from the global north.

They remind us, however, very importantly, that Latin America should not be seen merely as a (problematic) *receptor* of human rights thinking and law and an *object* of its concerns, but rather as *co-producer* of them, an active *subject* of philosophical, social and legal creations, innovations and transformations. Along the same lines, we may be able to say that the social organization, peace, and prosperity that modernity promised was conceived as much in Latin America as in Europe (QUIJANO, 2005).

As we have seen, theorists, politicians and legislators in both spaces discussed, created and mobilized language and frameworks of human rights in specific processes and as a horizon for political and legal projects, writings, structures of emancipation, freedom, development, dignity, solidarity, social equality.

Nonetheless, to complete our ecology of knowledge, we must turn our attention to the 'border thinking'¹⁰ (MIGNOLO & TLOSTANOVA, 2006). The knowledge that originated in the Latin American outside was established by the European colonial matrix of power.

¹⁰ 'Border thinking' is the knowledge that is produced at the borders, or outside, of the colonial matrix of power. This perspective is based on the premise that knowledge is geo-historically located, and that there is an epistemic differential rank between knowledge inside the colonial matrix - produced in the European imperial countries and

As above discussed, in Latin America, due to such a European cultural, ideological and ethnic rationality, the inside or the centre of the society was constituted of the religious and political elite of European (racial) descent and/or cultural belonging - the Christian priests and scholars, the creole elite that headed the processes of independence and manufactured the legal backbone of the newly born countries, and that historically governed the Latin American States, even in revolutionary processes such as the 1910 Mexican Revolution. This inside has historically been entitled to produce knowledge and regulations for social life and denied to the outside any right or legitimacy to this purpose. (QUIJANO, 2005)

As a consequence, outside of such an inside, we have the knowledge and social projects of the autochthonous communities, historically relegated to the realms of the primitive, magical and mythical, irrational and traditional (as opposed, respectively, to European civilized, scientific, rational and modern) (QUÍJANO, 2005). This is the knowledge of which contributions we will pursue in the following section.

3.5 THE LATIN AMERICAN BORDER THINKING CONTRIBUTIONS

Recently, such knowledge has been much sought after. In the *Modernity/Coloniality (M/C) group of studies*, since the 1960s, scholars of all the region have sought to unravel and deconstruct both Modernity and Coloniality, proposing a project for social sciences and society in search of and based on the social models of organization, knowledge and way of being from the groups who have been excluded, silenced in the structures and epistemic violence of the modern coloniality. (BALLESTRIN, 2013).

As arguably a development or unfolding of these decolonial studies, the *decolonial constitutional turns* of Ecuador (2007) and Bolivia (2008) have proposed charters that aim to refound the State with decolonizing paradigms, bringing to the forefront the traits of its societies, made of a coexistence of worldviews and cultural repertoires, traditions and

its languages (the UK, France, Germany, Spain, Portugal and Italy) - and that produced outside of it, in other countries and languages.

eISSN: 2675-3200

Cadernos de Pesquisa Direito Internacional sem Fronteiras, Vol. 2, N.2, 2020.

DOI:

Página 42 de 49

understandings of people, rights and duties previously silenced or denied by the monist State (SAMPAY, 1978).

Much could be talked about such contributions, but in terms of conceptions and sets of rights, two aspects seem to stand out and shall be henceforth discussed. One is the inscription or reframing of the rights and responsibilities of individuals and peoples, as well as the satisfaction of their needs, in a greater framework of life and living dimensions, to englobe, and in certain cases prioritize, the environment in which they live. In other words, *the reintegration of the complex cycle individual-society-nature*. Until then, previous epistemologies focused either on the individual elements of this chain or on the link between it and society, not forming up this cycle in its perspective. (MÉDICI, 2010a)

The roots of such a contribution is a native ancient Andean philosophy, alive among the indigenous peoples of the region, called *Sumak Kawsay*, in Quechua, or *Summa Quamaña*, in Aymara, *grosso modo*, 'well living', understood as a principle of living in conditions of dignity and fair coexistence between people, and between them and nature. Such a perspective sees nature as a living being and, more than that, as part of human lineage and life, and an ever-present ancestor, source of life, kin. (MAGALLANES & SHEELAN, 2017) The interactions between humans and nature, therefore, have to be mediated by the utmost respect and protection towards the sacred latter.

It is worth highlighting that in this perspective, nature is not seen as the source of the resources necessary for human life and wellbeing (its protection being an instrumentalist strategy, an inevitable underlying condition for human rights and wellbeing). Rather, primarily, nature is the dimension to which every possibility of personal and social welfare is intrinsically related, and thus depends upon. It is a part of the web of life, as much as humanity. (MÉDICI, 2010a/b)

The consequences of this articulation seem to be several, and of two orders, mainly. One is the precedence that nature has over men/women and society when there is a conflict. In

other words, the reframing of some problematic issues (such as development and neo-extractivism, for instance) to prioritize nature, since it is the basis on which human and social wellbeing can flourish. Thus, the *pro homine* principle of international human rights law metamorphoses into a *pro homine in natura*, or even into *pro natura*, depending on the concrete situation itself on which it is applied. This holistic or more communitarian conception gives rights to individuals and communities in nature and also to nature itself. (MÉDICI, 2010 a/b)

Another consequence of this contribution from this perspective is the correlated duties that derive from the reframing to the State in this cycle. Here, the State is constituted to be the body responsible for administering and providing these 'well living' conditions. It promotes and protects human and nature rights central to its fulfilment, watching over the people and the environment under its jurisdiction. Hence, the right to water, food and food security, health, housing, education, energy, communications, and social security are not merely abstract formulations, but direct responsibilities of the State to fulfil - universally, continuously, accessibly, efficaciously and equitably, according to its axiological matrix of 'well living'. (ALCOREZA, 2008)

The second contribution of Latin American border thinking that has been legally materialized is the *recognition of the social and cultural pluralism of society and the State*. In this line of thinking, the State bases its project on the ethnic plurality that constitutes it and on the intercultural dialogue between these multiple components, defining itself as a 'Plurinational State'. Various rights derive thereof, such as the right to cultural self-identification; the right to different regimes of property, work, education, and legislation; to communal practices, knowledge and institutions. In other words, different peoples in the State, historically subsumed in the theoretical unity/homogeneity of the colonial organization, are now called to be participants in the collective management of resources and services centred, in an equal position, and are to be rightfully protected to exist in their singularity. (MÉDICI, 2010a)

An unfolding of this contribution is the non-hierarchization of the peoples, their cultures and values composing the country and the rejection of a colonialist framing of interests/principles within the State itself and potentially in its relations with other countries. In other words, not discussed or not formally agreed to the incorporation of some peoples into the projects of another is no longer socially legitimate or constitutionally permitted. Likewise, the imposition, supremacy or precedence (for instance) of historically established liberal Western values - such as capital, democracy, rule of law, market economy - over traditional autochthonous concepts - such as mother earth, water, land, territory, self-determination, dignity, respect - is no longer admitted.

These contributions and their consequences, thus, show us the decolonial turn recently taken in parts of Latin America in social sciences and societies, human rights' thinking and practices. Additionally, they explicit the potential of emancipation and transformations that native indigenous' philosophies have in them and that can be realized by the establishment of an ecology of knowledge.

4 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article sought to relativize the so-called universality of human rights, which is based on the contributions of Western epistemologies, that have turned into hegemonic by imposing its colonial matrix of power in the period we have baptized Modernity.

Our analysis has worked in the frame of the Atlantic, in the oldest and longest colonial relations, involving Europe, as a centre, and Latin America, as periphery. In the spheres of power structures, social relations, and, more centrally to this analysis, knowledge and practices related to human rights, we have here attempted to show two main points. Firstly, how such claimed universality is actually partial and has silenced many perspectives. Secondly, how the emergence and hierarchization of understandings and concepts have had much to do with the historical development of the capitalist world-system, indissociable from colonialism and colonality, and how they have shaped societies, globally and within the different regions.

eISSN: 2675-3200

Cadernos de Pesquisa Direito Internacional sem Fronteiras, Vol. 2, N.2, 2020.

DOI:

Página 45 de 49

Also, as a necessary development, we have sought to hear such silenced perspectives, making justice to its contributions putting them into a fruitful and horizontal dialogue with the hegemonic ones. Getting to know and understand such contributions allows us to vividly see the gap left by one perspective presenting itself as total as well as to visualize the losses and waste of knowledge and practices it created. Consequently, it allows us to 'see possibilities not previously foreseen or deemed admissible theoretically' (SANTOS, 2014, p. 17) and expand our conception of human rights and beings, in individual, collective and environmental dimensions that are not otherwise imagined, contemplated, enacted, since they are not present in Western contributions.

This article is a first but very necessary step in the foremost pursuit of this project which is to contribute to an ecology of knowledge capable of building less incomplete universal human rights and of forming more complete human beings

REFERENCES

ALCOREZA, R. P. **Análisis de la nueva Constitución Política del Estado. Crítica y emancipación:** *Revista latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales*, 1. p. 35-50, 2008.

ANDRÉ-VINCENT, P. **La concrétisation de la notion classique de droit naturel à travers l'oeuvre de Las Casas**, In: *Las Casas et la politique des droits de l'homme, (actes de congrès)* 230. Aix-en-Provence, Bouches-du-Rhône: L'Institute d'études politiques éditions, 1974.

BALLESTRIN, L. **América Latina e o giro decolonial.** *Revista Brasileira de Ciência Política*, 1, p. 89-117. 2013

BARRAGÀN ROMANO, R. **La geografía diferencial de los derechos: entre la regulación del trabajo forzado en los países coloniales y la disociación entre trabajadores e indígenas en los Andes (1920-1954).** In: CARUSO, L; STAGNARO, A. *Una historia regional de la OIT. Aportes sobre regulación y legislación del trabajo latinoamericano*, La Plata: Universidad Nacional de La Plata: 2017. p. 25-63.

BEUCHOT, M. **Bartolomé de Las Casas, el humanismo indígena y los derechos humanos.** *Anuario Mexicano de historia del derecho*, v. 6, p. 37-48, 1994a.

_____. **Los fundamentos de los derechos humanos en Bartolomé de las Casas.** Barcelona: Anthropos Editorial, 1994b.

eISSN: 2675-3200

Cadernos de Pesquisa Direito Internacional sem Fronteiras, Vol. 2, N.2, 2020.

DOI:

Página 46 de 49

- BONAVIDES, P. **Do Estado liberal ao Estado Social**. 6. Malheiros: Ed. São Paulo, 1996.
- CÁRDENAS, Alejandro Soto. **Influencia de la independencia de los Estados Unidos en la constitución de las naciones latinoamericanas**. Washington: Organización de los Estados Americanos, 1979.
- CAROZZA, P. **From Conquest to Constitutions: Retrieving a Latin American Tradition of the Idea of Human Rights**. *Human Rights Quarterly*, 25, 2, p. 281-313. 2003.
- COLOMER VIADEL, A. **Introducción al constitucionalismo iberoamericano**. Madrid: Editorial Cultura Hispánica, 1990.
- D'ENTREVES, P. **Natural law**. London: Hutchinson, 1972
- DE LA TORRE RANGEL, J. S. **El reconocimiento del otro: raíz de una concepción integral e histórica de los derechos humanos**. *Anuario Mexicano de Historia del Derecho*, 6, p. 263-273, 1994.
- DE LAS CASAS, B. **Indian Freedom: The Cause of Bartolomé de Las Casas, 1484-1566: a Reader**. Kansas City: Rowman & Littlefield, 1995.
- DUSSEL, E. **Europa, modernidade e eurocentrismo**. In: LANDER, E. (Org.). *A colonialidade do saber: eurocentrismo e ciências sociais. Perspectivas latinoamericanas*. Buenos Aires: CLACSO, 2005. p. 24–32.
- ESPIELL, H. G. **El constitucionalismo latinoamericano y la codificación en el siglo XIX**. *Anuario iberoamericano de justicia constitucional*, n. 6, p. 143-176, 2002.
- GROSGOUEL, R. **Para descolonizar os estudos de economia política e os estudos pós-coloniais: transmodernidade, pensamento de fronteira e colonialidade global**. *Revista Crítica de Ciências Sociais*, n. 80, p. 115-147, 2008.
- GUTIÉRREZ, G. **Las Casas: In Search of the Poor of Jesus Christ**, trans. Robert R. Barr. Maryknoll, NY: Orbis, 1993.
- HUNT, L. **Inventing human rights: A history**. New York, London: WW Norton & Company, 2007.
- HELLER, A. **The Theory of Need in Marx**. London: Allison & Busby, 1976.
- ISHAY, M. R. **Human Rights and the Industrial Age: the development of a socialist perspective on human rights**. In: _____. *The History of Human Rights: From Ancient Times to the Globalization Era*. Berkeley; Los Angeles; London: University of California Press, 2008, p. 117-72.
- KENNEDY, D. **Primitive legal scholarship**. *Harvard International Law Journal*, v. 27, 1, 1986.

LESSNOFF, M. (org.) **Social Contract Theory**. Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1990.

MAGALLANES, C. I; SHEELAN, L. **Reframing Rights and Responsibilities to Prioritize Nature**. In: SCANLON, M. (ed.). *Law and Policy for a New Economy: Sustainable, Just, and Democratic*. Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar. 2017.

MÉDICI, A. **El nuevo constitucionalismo latinoamericano y el giro decolonial: Bolivia y Ecuador**. In: *Revista Derecho y Ciencias Sociales*, 3, p 3-23. 2010a.

_____. **Teoría constitucional y giro decolonial: narrativas y simbolismos de las constituciones. Reflexiones a propósito de la experiencia de Bolivia y Ecuador**. In: *Otros Logos. Revista de Estudios Críticos*, 1, p. 94-124. 2010b.

MERRYMAN, J. H; CLARK, D. S.; HALEY, J. O. **The Civil Law Tradition: Europe, Latin America and East Asia, cases and materials**. Matthew Bender, Charlottesville: Michie Co., 1994.

MIGNOLO, W. **La colonialidad a lo largo y a lo ancho**. In: LANDER. E. (org.). *La colonialidad del saber: eurocentrismo y ciencias sociales. Perspectivas latinoamericanas*. Buenos Aires: Clacso & Unesco, 2000, p. 55-85.

_____. **Desobediência Epistêmica: a opção descolonial e o significado de identidade em política**. Cadernos de Letras da UFF – Dossiê: Literatura, língua e identidade, [s.l.], n. 34, p. 287–324, 2008.

_____. **The Darker Side of Western Modernity: Global Futures, Decolonial Options**. Durham: Duke University Press, 2011.

_____. **The Idea of Latin America**. London & New York: Blackwell, 2005.

_____ & TLOSTANOVA, M. V. **Theorizing from the Borders: Shifting to Geo- and Body-Politics of Knowledge**. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 9 (2), p. 205–221. 2006.

NIEMEYER, E. V. **Revolution at Querétaro: The Mexican constitutional convention of 1916–1917**. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1974.

NORDAHL, R. **A Marxian approach to human rights**. In: AN-NA'IM, Abdullahi. *Human Rights in Cross-Cultural Perspectives: A Quest for Consensus*. p. 162-187. University of Pennsylvania Press, 1995.

NORIEGA, A. **La naturaleza de las garantías individuales en la Constitución de 1917**. Ciudad de México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1967.

PINHEIRO, M. C. B. **A Constituição de Weimar e os direitos fundamentais sociais: a preponderância da Constituição da República Alemã de 1919 na inauguração do constitucionalismo social à luz da Constituição Mexicana de 1917**. *Revista de informação legislativa*, 43 (169) p. 101-126. 2006.

eISSN: 2675-3200

Cadernos de Pesquisa Direito Internacional sem Fronteiras, Vol. 2, N.2, 2020.

DOI:

Página 48 de 49

QUIJANO, A. **Modernity, identity, and utopia in Latin America.** *Boundary 2*, 20 (3), p. 140-155, 1993.

_____. **Colonialidad del poder, cultura y conocimiento en América Latina.** *Anuario Mariateguiano*, 9, p. 113-21, 1997.

_____. **Colonialidade do poder, eurocentrismo e América Latina.** In: LANDER, E. (Org.). *A colonialidade do saber: eurocentrismo e ciências sociais. Perspectivas latinoamericanas.* Buenos Aires: CLACSO, 2005. p. 107–130.

RAMOS, F. Y. **The social rights enshrined in the Mexican constitution of 1917.** *Int'l Lab. Rev.*, v. 96, 1967.

SAMPAY, A. **La legitimidad de la constitución.** In: *Realidad Económica*, 30, p. 42-65. 1978.

SANTOS, B. de S. **La globalización del derecho. Los nuevos caminos de la regulación y la emancipación.** Bogotá: Universidad Nacional de Colombia e IILSA, 1998.

_____. **A crítica da razão indolente. Contra o desperdício da experiência.** Porto: Edições Afrontamento, 2000.

_____. **Para descolonizar el Occidente: más allá del pensamiento abismal.** Buenos Aires: CLACSO, 2010.

_____. **Epistemologies of the south: justice against epistemicide.** London and New York: Routledge, 2014.

_____. CHAUI, M. **Direitos humanos, democracia e desenvolvimento.** 1. ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 2014.

TIERNEY, B. **The Idea of Natural Rights: Studies on Natural Rights, Natural Law and Church Law 1150-1625.** Michigan, Cambridge: Emory University press, 1997.

WALLERSTEIN, I. **The modern world-system. 3 vols.** Berkeley, Los Angeles, London: Univ of California Press, 2011.

WEINREB, L. **Natural law and justice.** Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1987.

YEPES, J. M. **La Evolución del Pensamiento Constitucional de la América Latina (1810-1830).** In: *El Pensamiento Constitucional de Latinoamérica 3. 1810-1830.* 95, 99. Bogotá: Academia Nacional de la Historia, 1962.

ZAVALA, S. A. **The defence of human rights in Latin America: sixteenth to eighteenth centuries.** Paris: Unesco Publications, 1964.